

Table 2. Regeneration ability of plants from inflorescence-derived calli of IR31662-47-2-1.

Explant length (cm)	Days to form green plantlet	Regeneration (%)
DS ₁ (0.5)	23	74.2
DS ₂ (1)	20	65.0
DS ₃ (2)	26	40.6
DS ₄ (3)	25	25.2
DS ₅ (4)	23	22.8
DS ₆ (5)	21	19.0

Pest resistance—diseases

Evolution of rice blast (BI) fungus based on cross-fertility of *Pyricularia grisea* Sac.

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We collected 500 monoconidial isolates of *P. grisea* from rice-growing regions of Yunnan Province, China. These isolates were crossed with standard isolates 57-R-33 (MAT1-1) and 57-R-28 (MAT1-2), both of which were isolated from *Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn. Results showed that geographic environment and rice type influenced cross-fertility of *P. grisea*: in southern Yunnan, it was more than 60%, and in the high-altitude cold region where japonicas are grown, it was only 10%. Twenty-six isolates that produced perithecia and ascospores were selected for further study. (See table for location, hosts, mating type, perithecial formation by single culture of isolates, and rate of perfect state formation.)

Ten isolates of MAT1-1 were crossed with 16 isolates of MAT1-2. Although isolates crossed with the mating standard isolates produced ascospores, the cross-fertility of these isolates was remarkably different. Isolate YL 90-84 crossed with all fertile isolates. Y88-285 did not produce any ascospores in any cross combinations, although a few produced sterile perithecia. Number of

hormones might be an integral component of media for successful subcultures.

In the regeneration experiment, 2,4-D was completely withdrawn and replaced with IAA. Appearance of green plantlets was fastest with 1-cm-long young inflorescences and slowest with 2-cm-long inflorescences. Regeneration frequency notably varied with

developmental stage of the explant. Highest regeneration frequency occurred in 0.5-cm-long young inflorescences and lowest frequency in 5-cm-long inflorescences (Table 2).

Young inflorescences are a good source for rice tissue culture. They have efficient callus induction and redifferentiation frequencies. ■

perithecia produced varied greatly with combinations of isolates. In general, the fertile isolates with wide cross-fertility also showed higher cross-fertility, producing more perithecia and ascospores compared with other isolates.

Isolates with greatest mating competence, YL 90-84 (MAT1-2) and YL 90-71, YL 90-90, YL 90-80, YL 90-77, and others (MAT1-1), were all isolated from upland rice in Xishuangbanna, southern Yunnan province. Single cultures of these isolates, except YL 90-84, produced sterile perithecia on oatmeal agar at 22 °C with

continuous illumination. The process of perithecial formation conformed with the formation process of perithecium in mating and also the perithecium-like structure produced by single cultures of *Pyricularia* from *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. and *E. coracana* (L.) Gaertn. The perithecia produced by single cultures had two common characteristics: they were derived from isolates with higher cross-fertility, and they formed two bands of perithecia. These isolates were all hermaphrodites. We speculate that *Pyricularia* might have evolved from

Location, host source, race, and mating type of *Pyricularia grisea*. Yunnan Province, China.

Isolate	Location	Host source		Race	Mating	P ^b	R ^c
		Variety	Type ^a				
YL 90-7	Mojiang	Dalixian 40	I	016-t	MAT1-2	-	40.0
YL 90-10	Mojiang	Luoping	?	136	MAT1-2	-	10.0
YL 90-11	Mojiang	Luoping	?	136	MAT1-2	-	20.0
YL 90-13	Mojiang	Luoping	?	036	MAT1-2	-	50.0
YL 90-175	Jingping	Gaoshanzaogu	?	106	MAT1-2	-	40.0
YL 90-51	Jingping	Luopinggu	?	016	MAT1-2	-	30.0
YL 90-52	Jingping	Luoping	?	117	MAT1-2	-	50.0
YL 90-84	Jinghong	Unknown	U	134-t	MAT1-2	-	100.0
YL 90-71	Jinghong	Unknown	U	102	MAT1-1	+	87.5
YL 90-74	Jinghong	Unknown	U	116	MAT1-1	+	43.8
YL 90-77	Jinghong	Unknown	U	102	MAT1-1	+	43.8
YL 90-80	Jinghong	Unknown	U	136-t	MAT1-1	+	62.5
YL 90-90	Jinghong	Unknown	U	116	MAT1-1	+	75.0
Y88-685	Maguang	D-you 63	I	0	MAT1-2	-	20.0
Y88-285	Liuku	Yunjing 134	J	017	MAT1-2	-	0.0
Y88-282	Liuku	Nuogu	J	037-t	MAT1-2	-	70.0
Y88-249	Tengchong	74-35	J	0	MAT1-2	-	40.0
13-1	Tengchong	74-35	J	0	MAT1-2	-	60.0
5-1	Qujing	Chujing 3	J	016-t	MAT1-2	-	30.0
5-2	Qujing	Chujing 3	J	016-t	MAT1-2	-	60.0
5-5	Qujing	Chujing 3	J	016-t	MAT1-2	-	30.0
45-1	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	6.3
45-2	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	12.5
45-3	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	18.8
45-4	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	18.8
45-5	Jinghong	Luexi	U	136	MAT1-1	-	37.5

^aI = indica, U = upland rice, J = japonica, ? = unknown. ^bP = perithecia production in single culture. + = produced, - = not produced. ^cR = rate of perfect state formation.

homothallism to heterothallism and then to the infertile state in which the sexual function might have been lost.

Southern Yunnan Province is a center of rice origin and has a long history of upland rice cultivation. The possibility that parasitic differentiation could be established from grasses to cultivated

rice (H. Kato's hypotheses) might have occurred in this area. The *Pyricularia* in this area exhibit the same properties as those of grass isolates (*E. indica*, *E. coracana*). Many isolates produced a lot of perithecia and produced sterile perithecia in single culture (see table). The formation rate of *Pyricularia*

becomes gradually less from south to north—from temperate to cool to cold regions—until it cannot form. The trend from high to low fertility corresponds with direction of the spread of rice cultivation. ■

Reaction of some rice germplasm to leaf blast (BI) in Guyana

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Blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* is an important rice disease in Guyana. We screened 377 breeding lines for leaf BI resistance during Aug and Sep 1991. Breeding lines were grown in International Rice Blast Nurseries to score leaf BI reactions. Highly BI-susceptible variety Rustic was used as susceptible check and in spreader rows. Varieties Diwani and 6039 served as resistant checks.

Entries were inoculated at the four-leaf stage with chopped infected leaves. Nursery beds were irrigated twice a day between 1000 and 1100 h, and 1500 and 1600 h. Beds were covered with polyethylene sheets at night to maintain high humidity.

Reaction of rice breeding lines to blast (BI) in Guyana, 1991.

Breeding line	BI score ^a	BI reaction ^b	Origin	Breeding line	BI score ^a	BI reaction ^b	Origin
CT8008-3-5-2P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR54791-19-2-3	1	R	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-5P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56382-123-3-1	3	MR	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-6P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56383-46-1-2-1	3	MR	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-7P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56446-94-3-1-2	1	R	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-8P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR8 F ₂ -1-3-2	3	MR	Guyana
CT8222-4-1-8P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR8 F ₂ -2-3-1	3	MR	Guyana
CT8238-6-14-P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR9 F ₂ -1-3-2	5	MS	Guyana
CT8285-13-1-3P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR12 F ₂ -1-2-3	5	MS	Guyana
CT8285-13-5-2P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR126 F ₂ -2-1-1	3	MR	Guyana
Diwani	3	MR		NAR126 F ₄ -2-5-2	5	MS	Guyana
Surinam				NAR151 F ₄ -4-3	5	MS	Guyana
Eloni	3	MR		NAR210-1-1-4	1	R	Guyana
Surinam				NAR210-1-4	1	R	Guyana
IR8192-31-2-1-2	3	MR	IRRI	NAR218-2-4-4	3	MR	Guyana
IR44624-127-1-2-2-3	3	MR	IRRI	Pedigree 9	3	MR	Guyana
IR47761-27-1-36	1	R	IRRI	Pedigree 12	3	MR	Guyana
IR51678-93-2-2	5	MS	IRRI	TX06	5	MS	USA
IR52350-93-2-2	3	MR	IRRI	TX49 (Aromatic Lemont)	3	MR	USA
IR53306-36-1-3-1	1	R	IRRI	6039	3	MR	Guyana
IR53306-64-1-3-2	3	MR	IRRI				
IR53649-AC5-2	1	R	IRRI				

^aScored (0-9) using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, and MS = moderately susceptible.

Entries were scored on a scale of 0-9 using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when the susceptible check had scored 7-9. Sixteen lines were resistant,

16 lines moderately resistant, and 6 lines moderately susceptible under conditions conducive to severe disease development (see table). ■

Resistance of BPH-resistant rice varieties to *S. furcifera* in the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and modified seedbox screening test (MSST).^a

Variety	Genes for resistance to BPH	Plant damage rating ^b	
		SSST	MSST
IR47-B2-6	<i>Bph1</i>	9.0 a	9.0 a
Mudgo	<i>Bph1</i>	1.8 bc	1.0 a
Ptb18	<i>bph2</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph3</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Gambada Samba	<i>bph4</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Babawee	<i>bph4</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
ARC10550	<i>bph5</i>	1.8 bc	1.0 b
Swamalata	<i>bph6</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
Ptb21	<i>bph2 + Bph3</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Ptb33	<i>bph2 + Bph3</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
IR26	<i>Bph1</i>	9.0 a	9.0 a
IR36	<i>bph2</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
IR56	<i>Bph3</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
IR62	<i>Bph3</i>	2.2 b	1.0 b
IR64	<i>Bph1</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
TN1	No gene	9.0 a	9.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT; av of 5 replications.

^bDamage was rated on a 0-9 scale where 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately resistant, and 7-9 = susceptible.

Pest resistance— insects

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper (*Sogatella furcifera*) in rice varieties with different genes for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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We evaluated 15 BPH-resistant rice varieties for resistance to *S. furcifera* using the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and modified seedbox screening test (MSST). The experiment was laid out